

METHODOLOGICAL BASIS AND COMPONENTS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS MUSICAL SKILLS

Sobirov Navruzбек Khakimjonovich

Acting Associate Professor at the State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10927510>

Abstract. *In the world's educational and research institutions, scientific research is being conducted on the development of criteria for performing and artistic mastery in the art of music, and the direct improvement of national music. Particular attention is paid to scientific research on improving connections in the art of music. fields of drama, comedy, establishing international cooperation in this area and effectively using the capabilities of music and art, introducing innovations in this area.*

Keywords: *musicality, methodological basis, component*

From scientific research conducted on a global scale, it is known that every nation has its own traditions and values. Musicology is an invaluable asset to the world community. That is why musical culture plays a role in the development of each person as an individual. Along with the influence of music on social life, it is also a factor in the formation of a child's personality, instilling in him such feelings as humanity and patriotism.

In the development of the human personality, art, art, music acquires a historical character, and in this regard, scientific and didactic resources were created by such thinkers as Avesta, Kaykovus, Abu Raikhan Beruni, Mahmud Koshgari, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Alisher Navoi. Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur is important.

In the spiritual and educational reforms of our independent country, the active participation of creative workers and the education of young people as a loyal and comprehensively developed generation are of great importance. An invaluable role in the education of such spiritually mature people is played by methodological classes on the development of musical skills of students of higher educational institutions and non-group artistic and musical circles. Based on the tasks set for methodological classes on the development of musical skills of students of higher educational institutions, we recommend dividing this important work into three parts:

	Properties	
Teaching	Bringing -up	Development

The task of learning is one of the main and decisive issues, while acquiring all the necessary knowledge about music (choral performance in a group), performance of amateur artistic groups outside the group, applying this knowledge in practice, and developing skills.

The task of education is an integral part of an integrated approach to the overall process of the teaching method with the tasks of education and development. The main goal of education is to convey the content of the lesson to the younger generation through various methods and ensure a correct perception of their place in society.

The main goal of the development is to develop the ability to comprehend the knowledge acquired during undergraduate music education and among creative enthusiasts, and to teach them to draw the right conclusions from various scientific and cultural information. This process works to gradually teach undergraduate music education students how to think creatively.

The main goal of this task in the teaching style is the formation of the ideological, scientific, political and cultural consciousness of students of pre-university music education. In the process of learning performing arts (singer, musician), the mental and creative abilities of amateur students, their will, and the qualities necessary for their maturity develop. These problems cannot be solved in isolation. All of them are carried out comprehensively, interdependently during the training process. Based on the knowledge and skills of performance, the worldview of the participants in the student-amateur group of the undergraduate music education course is formed, and the problems of music education are solved. Today the battle is on to win the hearts and minds of young people around the world. This struggle is not waged with military weapons, but through the media. It's no secret that most of the information disseminated around the world serves certain purposes. In such a situation, the instruction of the head of our state that we need to fight idea with idea, idea with idea, ignorance with ignorance is very useful. It is impossible to mislead our self-confident peers, who are proud of their ancestors and who fully imagine the bright future of the country. Therefore today

It is necessary to pay special attention to strengthening the faith of young people in cultural and educational trainings and events.

A bachelor's degree in music education influences the student's emotional and aesthetic sense and helps to actively develop it. The Bachelor of Music Education also touches the soul of the student and plays an important role in shaping his moral and aesthetic character. Therefore, the main goal is to improve the musical abilities of undergraduate music education students, cultivate a musical culture that is an integral part of their spiritual culture, and prepare them for independent life. To achieve these goals, students of higher educational institutions of musical culture face the following tasks:

- to increase interest in the art of music among undergraduate students in music education;
- musical composition - artistic taste, mastery of the creativity of Uzbek hafiz and the formation of the need for various musical activities;
- compiling a set of knowledge and skills about writing music;
- development of a sense of artistic creativity in the process of musical activity;
- moral and aesthetic education of music education students through the artistic and ideological content of works;
- during music lessons and extracurricular activities, cultivate enthusiasm for the profession and work.

The level of professionalism of students of higher educational institutions is of great importance in the implementation of these tasks.

In our opinion, the practical significance of research work is based on the developmental component:

the entire system of teaching students of higher educational institutions the skill of musical performance is clearly focused on activating the educational process, awakening students' initiative and developing their creativity;

Based on the methods, conditions, criteria and components of the development of their professional knowledge, skills and creative qualities in the process of preparing musical performance of students, improving the quality of musical performance of students of higher educational institutions is a recommendation on their own terms;

select a set of tasks, forms in relation to the specific conditions for obtaining such a specialty and represent executive techniques that ensure that the process of increasing the level of professional training is taken into account.

Our research on the methodological development of students' musical abilities shows the high effectiveness of models, technologies and the curriculum of musical training and performance of students in the formation and development of professional knowledge, skills, abilities, and creative personal qualities. showed and confirmed the feasibility of their use in the training of students of higher educational institutions - musicians.

REFERENCES

1. Форобий Абу Наср. Фозил одамлар шахри. - Т.: Ғ. Ғулом номидаги Адабиёт ва санъат нашриёти, 1993; Форобий Абу Наср. Рисолалар. - Т.: Фан, 1975; Беруний Абу Райҳон. Қадимги халқлардан қолган ёдгорликлар. Танланган асарлар. 1-жилд. - Т.: Фан, 1968; Абу Али Ибн Сино. Тиб қонунлари. Уч жилдлик. - Т.: А.Қодирий номидаги халқ мероси нашриёти, 1994; Амир Темур. Темур тузуклари.- Т.: Ғ.Ғулом номидаги Адабиёт ва санъат
2. Ибрагимов Э.Х. Маънавий-руҳий манипуляциянинг ёшлар дунёқарашига таъсири: Фалс.ф. бўйича фалс.д. (PhD) дисс.автореф.- Самарқанд: СамДУ, 2020.